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Sources:

1. Kuipers, Aert H. *The Squamish Language: Grammar, Texts, Dictionary*. The Hague: Mouton & Co., 1967.

-note: Kuipers phonemic/phonetic characters and their (IPA) equivalents (I think) as follows:

C°	C ^w (labialized)
C'	C ^ʔ (glottalized)
u	w
i	j
x̣	X (chi)
K	any obstruent
R	normally any sonorant
A	any full vowel (not ə)
'	follows a stressed V

-no initial vowels (epenthetic glottal stop if a V would otherwise be word initial) (p. 22)

Stress (p. 23)

-stress not restricted to a part of a word

-longer words may have 2 stressed segments, alternative stresses, or an optional second stressed segment

-clitics (clitic remains undefined) are not stressed, but part of the stress unit they are connected to (he doesn't discuss how to know this)

-but sometimes clitics can be stressed, for example for emphasis, or if they have an adverbial suffix, or as an enclitic.

-clitics are very prone to vowel reduction (p. 43)

-optional clitic initial glottal stop deletion:

ʔ → [ə~ʔ] / C_[-voiced]-

-vowel reduction (to ə) - unstressed vowels in longer words often reduced (p. 35)

examples (stressed vowels marked with an apostrophe directly after the stressed vowel, as in Kuipers' text, since syllable boundaries are apparently unknown):

/mə'lalus/ → [mʌ'lalos, mʌ'lələs] 'raccoon'

/stəwəqin/ → [stōwəqɛjn, stōwəqɛn, stōwəqɛn] 'graveyard'

-progressive vowel assimilation: stressed V can sometimes influence following V

(including the V in a following suffix) (p. 36)

examples using the transitivity marker -(V)n:

/mə's-ŋ/ 'glue together-transitive'

/c' aq' -an/ 'hit-trans'

/mu'j-un/ 'soak-trans'

/li'k^w-in/ 'hang up-trans'

-geminates across morpheme boundaries regularly and/or optionally merge (p. 39)

-svarabhakti/anaptyctic vowels (p. 41):

ø → [ə, æ] / #_C_[uvular]

-favorite root-morpheme skeleton (p. 45):

-/C₁VC₂/

where C₁ can also be /ʔ/

and C₂ can also be /ʔ/ or /Rʔ/ where R=sonorant

- see section 57 for restrictions
- also possible
 - /CVh/ or /CV:/ (p. 46)
 - /CVR(?)/ where R=/h, ʉ, i/ (p. 47)
 - longer root morphemes (p. 49):
 - most frequent /C₁VC₂C₃/ with C₁ and C₂ as above and C₃ ≠ /h, ʉ, i/
 - but also /C₁VC₂R/ where R=/(m), n, l/
 - and/or /C₁VC₂A(?)/ where A≠ə
 - plus, C₁ can be CC if C is not a sonorant (p. 50)
- prefix (few) skeletons (p. 50): C-, CC-, CV-, CVC-
- suffix (many) skeletons (p. 50): -C, -CC, -CVC, -VC, -VCVC, -VCCV
- glottalization is "easily dropped", especially in /R?/ (p. 51)

NOTE: pp 51-52 are partially missing from this copy of the grammar)

Note: Kuiper's use of 'word-initially' does not seem to include clitics:
 "In a few cases geminates occur word-initially, e.g. in the phrase /ʉa_λ-s_ʉa_n.na'/?/ 'where they (persons) come from'; here /n.na'/?/ is a form of the morpheme /na'/?/ 'at'..." (p. 41)

Note on clitics: "clitics occur very frequently in texts, and in the large majority of cases they form a stress-unit with the word that follows them" and "...rules for unstressed vowels apply in the same way to clitics, except that the tendency to reduction is even stronger..." and "...sometimes groups of clitics tend to merge into simplified forms" (pp. 42-3)

Reduplication (pp. 98...):

- 2 types: total and partial
- 2 types of partial: initial and final
- reduplication generally "concerns root-elements rather than affixes" (p. 98)
- Total reduplication (at most first two consonants are reduplicated):

C₁VC₂- C₁(V)C₂

/s-taqi'u/ → /s-təq-taqi'u/ (horse → horses; s- is a nominalizer)

-sub-types of total reduplication:

Ia. C₁AC₂- C₁AC₂

Ib. C₁AC₂- C₁(ə)C₂

IIa. C₁əC₂- C₁AC₂

IIb. C₁əC₂- C₁(ə)C₂

both versions of type I are not productive and stress is not involved in reduplication, while both versions of type II stress remains on the second member unless monosyllabic stem with ə, then it's on the first member

/lam'/?/ → /lm:la'm'/?/ 'house → houses'

/mən'/?/ → /mə'n?:mn/ 'child → children'

-Partial reduplication:

-initial: C₁V- C₁(V)C₂

-final: C₁(V)C₂- VC₂